

The human traffic mill

Collaborative justice and community-oriented policing deprive the rights of the accused and interfere with critical state emergency management systems response and reporting requirements.

1. **DO NOT** encourage arbitrary law enforcement.
2. **DO NOT** pass government encroachment off to third-party middlemen.
3. **DO NOT** fund interests that favor displacement and nonfeasance in criminal law enforcement.
4. **DO** respect the privacy and rights of the accused.

We are a constitutional nation. There is no place for "alternative justice." Without rights and process of the law, I am no longer citizen. I am chattel. - [Onlyfans.com/dirtydoves](https://www.onlyfans.com/onlyfans.com/dirtydoves) May 2023.